

Emergent Transition from Radial Foraging to Tree-like Raiding Patterns Induced by Complete Following for Pheromone

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Abstract: Among ants that show complex and diverse collective actions, army ants are known to raid prey in groups. It has been confirmed that the characteristic pattern in a swarm raid of army ants changes from radial to tree-like with time. There are some simulation studies focusing only on the emergence of tree-like patterns. However, the models adopted in their simulations cannot represent the transition of patterns from radial to tree-like observed in the real world. In this study, we propose an army ant model with a modification of the model adopted by Solé et al. and clarify the conditions of the emergence of the transition. From the experimental simulation results of our model, we deduce that the simple modification of the Solé model can move individuals in eight directions, but it is not enough to express multidirectional to unidirectional convergence. Additionally, our simulation experiments showed that for the pattern transition from radial to tree-like, it is necessary for the individuals to keep moving forward until they get food, and for the returning individual to completely follow the pheromone.

Keywords: army ant model, radial foraging pattern, tree-like raiding pattern, swarm raid, complete following for pheromone.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social insects are known to perform collective actions in cooperation with other individuals. Ants that are social insects are observed to exhibit complex and diverse collective action. The ants are observed in a wide variety of ecology, including species that nest on the ground and trees, those that feed on other insects, and those that feed on mold.

Army ants are known to raid prey collectively [1, 3] among the ants showing diverse ecology. As shown in Fig. 1, in the swarm raids of army ants, a tree-like pattern continuing from the nesting area referred to as the bivouac is observed. The early stage of the raid spreads in multiple directions radially (Fig. 1(a)), and with time, it is observed that it converges in one direction (Fig. 1(c)). Assuming that this state transitions from multiple directions to one direction are obtained through evolution, they are considered to be a result of adaptation to some environment. We are yet to know exactly the kind of environment in which we can obtain such state transitions as a result of adaptation.

Fig. 1 Time evolution of the swarm raiding patterns in *Ecton burchelli* [6]. This figure is scanned from [6].

Deneubourg et al. [4] and Solé et al. [2] attempted to clarify how a tree-like pattern as shown in Fig. 1(b) and (c) is generated from interactions among ants. Deneubourg et al. showed the emergence of tree-like patterns using a simulation model in which individual ants make a choice between the direction of the left front and the right front and move on a lattice in a two-dimensional lattice space. Additionally, Solé et al. changed the model of Deneubourg et al. into a model in

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which individual ants move around on a two-dimensional lattice space while selecting one of the three front directions. However, because the Deneubourg and Solé models are limited to forward movement, they cannot express multidirectional to unidirectional convergence observed in the real world as shown in Fig. 1(a).

Because the Solé model proceeds only in one direction, it is considered possible to represent movement in multiple directions, that is, a radial pattern, by determining the various directions of movement when exiting from the bivouac. Moreover, because the pheromone is not newly laid when there is no food, the concentration of pheromone is different in the cases with and without the food, and it is thought that the pattern changes from radial to tree-like.

Furthermore, there are some studies using simulations by ant models [7-9], but these are not focused to clarify conditions for emerging transition from radial to tree-like patterns.

The purpose of this study is to examine whether a collective raid with a pattern transition from radial to tree-like will be generated using a modified Solé model in which each ant can select one of the various directions when exiting their bivouac, and to clarify the conditions for the emergence of the transition.

II. ARMY ANT MODEL

A. Solé model

The Solé model is a model in which identical individuals move on a discrete two-dimensional lattice space. Two types of states, which are the state of coming out of the bivouac and the state of returning to the bivouac, are respectively defined as in the Eq. (1),

$$S = \begin{cases} 1 & (\text{exploring}), \\ 2 & (\text{returning}). \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

An individual in state $S=1$, i.e., an individual who is exploring for food out of the bivouac, releases one unit of pheromone after moving, as long as the pheromone concentration does not exceed threshold σ_1 . Similarly, an individual in state $S=2$, that is, an individual who is returning to the bivouac with food, releases q units of pheromone after moving, unless the pheromone concentration exceeds threshold σ_2 . The pheromone is updated as in Eq. (2) in each step,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(x, y) &\rightarrow (1 - \delta)\phi(x, y), \\ \phi(x, y) &\geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\phi(i, j)$ is the pheromone concentration at coordinates (x, y) , and δ is the decay rate.

Furthermore, whether each individual moves or not probabilistically is defined as Eq. (3). As shown in Fig. 2, $\phi(x+1, y+1)$, $\phi(x, y+1)$ and $\phi(x-1, y+1)$ represent the pheromone concentrations of the three squares in front of position (x, y) where the individual is located.

Fig. 2 An individual's probabilistic movement toward three front directions in the Solé model.

$$\begin{aligned} P &= \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \tanh\left(\frac{\Phi}{\phi^*}\right) \right] \\ \Phi &= \phi(x+1, y+1) \\ &+ \phi(x, y+1) \\ &+ \phi(x-1, y+1) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where P is the movement probability of an individual, and ϕ^* represents the pheromone concentration such that the movement probability per step is 0.5. In this study, the value adopted in the Solé one is followed and $\phi^*=100$ is set. When we decided to move by the probability movement, the next individual decides also where to move. The destination site is determined by the three probabilities π_L , π_C , and π_R . The probabilities π corresponding to the left, center, and right are defined as Eq. (4).

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_L &= \frac{1}{C} [\mu + \phi(x-1, y+1)]^2, \\ \pi_C &= \frac{1}{C} [\mu + \phi(x, y+1)]^2, \\ \pi_R &= \frac{1}{C} [\mu + \phi(x+1, y+1)]^2. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here, C used in Eq. (4) is defined as Eq. (5).

$$\begin{aligned}
 C &= [\mu + \phi(x + 1, y + 1)]^2 \\
 &+ [\mu + \phi(x, y + 1)]^2 \\
 &+ [\mu + \phi(x - 1, y + 1)]^2,
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5}$$

where μ is referred to as the attraction rate and is a parameter that indicates how much the individual is attracted to the pheromone-free site.

B. Eight-ways model

In this study, we propose the eight-way model. This model is a modified Solé model in which all individuals can select one direction of eight when the individuals move out of the bivouac into the field. Individuals in the Solé model detect the three pheromones in front of the model to determine the destination of the movement even when leaving the bivouac.

However, in the Eight-ways model, as shown in Fig. 3(a), the eight positions around the bivouac are sensed only when leaving to determine the direction to proceed. If the decision is to move in the direction of position B, the pheromone of the front three positions X, Y, and Z are sensed to decide the position to move to as shown in Fig. 3(b). After the direction is determined, the individual moves by sensing the pheromone on the front three or two positions as with the Solé model as illustrated in Fig. 3(b). When moving in an oblique direction (A, C, F, H in Fig. 3(a)), if the individual moves by sensing the pheromone of the front three positions, the individual will be concentrated at the center under the influence of the pheromone of the previous time.

Fig. 3 Difference between areas that can sense the pheromone before and after leaving the bivouac in our eight-ways model. Fig. 3(a) shows the range of the pheromone that can be sensed when leaving the bivouac. Fig. 3(b) shows the range of the pheromone that can be sensed after leaving the bivouac.

The reason why the individual in the leading group decides and develops the new direction of the pheromone trail is that it will be concentrated at the center position as illustrated in Fig. 4(a) to 4(d). For example, in case the individual moves from position C in Fig. 3(a), the moving-destination candidate of time t will become three positions X, Y, and Z in Fig. 4(a). As shown in Fig. 4(b), the candidates for the move destination from the three positions X, Y, and Z at time $t+1$ are six positions with diagonal lines or dots. Because the position Y was a move destination candidate at time t , there is a possibility that more pheromones has already been added to position Y by some individuals than in other positions. Therefore, at time $t+1$, the individual that exists in the positions X and Z move easily to position Y. Fig. 4(c) shows the moving-destination candidates at time $t+2$. The positions with dots also have the pheromones, which were attached at the previous time. As can be observed in Fig. 4(d), the number of positions with pheromones added by some individuals is increased in the moving destination candidate of time $t+3$.

Fig. 4 A problem in which the individual in the leading group that decides and develops new direction of pheromone trail concentrates on the center when moving in an oblique direction. The positions with blue dots are positions in which pheromones are laid that are candidates for the moving destinations. The positions with green diagonal lines can sense pheromones and are candidates for moving destinations.

To solve the problem that the leading individuals concentrate on the center position when moving in the oblique direction, in our model, when it is decided that an individual goes in an oblique direction, the individual senses the pheromone of the two squares in

front to decide the destination. As shown in Fig. 5(a), If the leading individual moves from position C, the moving destination candidates of the time t will become the two positions of X and Z based on the solution of the problem. Fig. 5(b) shows the positions with diagonal lines as the movement destination candidates at time $t+1$. None of the two candidates of movement from the position X or Z had a pheromone attached at the previous time. Similarly, as shown in Fig. 5(c) and 5(d), no pheromone is attached to any destination candidate positions at time $t+2$ and $t+3$.

Fig. 5 A solution by sensing the pheromone of two positions in front when moving in the oblique direction for the problem that the leading individuals concentrate to the center position. As with Fig. 4, the positions with green diagonal lines are positions that can sense the pheromones and become moving destination candidates.

III. RESULTS

A. Settings of simulation experiments

Various parameters of the simulation experiments were set as listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Settings of simulation experiments.

Map size	500 × 500
Bivouac position	(250, 250)
The number of ants that can exist in one position	30
The amount of pheromone q released by an individual with $S = 2$	75
The threshold σ_1 at which an individual with $S = 1$ stops to release pheromone.	50
The threshold σ_2 at which an individual with $S = 2$ stops to release pheromone.	700
The decay rate δ for pheromone	0.0032
The attraction rate μ for position	100

B. Results of simulation experiments

The first experiment using our model defined in the section II-B shows that the individual is heading in a direction that is clearly different from that of the food. The results are shown in Fig. 6. The bivouac is located at the center of the graph, from which individuals are released on the map. The blue dots indicate the food, and the red dots indicate the individuals. The color of the red dots becomes dense as the number of individuals is increased in the position of the individuals. Although the food is placed in the lower left and upper right, it can be observed that the individual is concentrated in the right and lower right directions.

Fig. 6 An example of individuals' movements heading in the different directions from the directions in which the foods exist. The bivouac is located at the center of the graph, from which individuals are released on the map. Blue dots indicate food, and red dots indicate individuals. The color of red dots becomes dense, as the number of individuals is increased in the position with individuals. Although the food is placed in the lower left and upper right, it can be observed that the individual is concentrated in the right and lower right directions.

Fig.7 shows the results of arranging the food only at the upper right and coloring only the individuals headed for the upper right. Blue dots indicate food; the individuals headed for only the upper right are represented by red dots, and gray dots on the others, as shown in Fig. 7. Because the individual that should have gone to the upper right is seen at the lower left, it can be observed that the individual cannot enter the bivouac and has flowed to the lower left.

From these results, we can deduce that if the food cannot enter the bivouac, the behavior of many

individuals is affected, resulting in a strange behavior as a whole.

Therefore, we set a new rule for our model. The rule is that individuals with $S=2$ who entered the range of several position around the bivouac, are forcibly returned to the bivouac. Fig. 8 shows the result of setting an individual that has entered the range to some extent around the bivouac to be forced back to the bivouac. From Fig. 8, the individuals in the range of some extent around the bivouac are returned to the bivouac. However, few red individuals can be seen in the lower left of the bivouac.

Fig. 7 An example of movement of individuals that colored only individuals going to the upper right when the food is placed at only the upper right. Blue dots indicate food, the individuals headed for only the upper right are represented by red dots, and gray dots on the others. Because the individual that should have gone to the upper right is seen at the lower left, it can be observed that the individual cannot enter the bivouac and has flowed to the lower left.

Fig. 8 A few individuals who cannot return to bivouac after applying the new rules. Blue dots indicate food, the individuals directly headed for the upper right from the bivouac are represented by red dots, and gray dots on the other ones. The individuals in the range of some extent around the bivouac are returned to the bivouac automatically. However, it can be observed that a few red individuals are in the lower left.

Additionally, Figs. 9 and 10 show the pheromone concentrations on the periphery of the bivouac and on the entire map, respectively. The trail of strong pheromones released by the individual with food is tied to the bivouac. However, it can be observed that the trail flows to the lower left because the width of the trail was expanded.

Fig. 9 Pheromone concentrations on periphery of the bivouac. The central position is the bivouac. When individuals at the upper right are returned to the bivouac, the returning individuals are lay pheromones at one position in front of the bivouac position so that the individuals on the bivouac can sense them. Additionally, because the pheromone is strongly attached to the upper side, the right side, and the upper right side, it can be deduced that the individual that went to the upper right is spread to the upper side or the right side.

Fig. 10 The pheromone concentration on the entire map after applying the new rule. The positions with many pheromones are plotted in red and dark red. The trail of strong pheromones released by the individual with food is tied to the bivouac. However, it can be observed that the trail flows to the lower left because the width of trail was expanded.

From these results, it can be observed that although some individuals can return to the bivouac, some individuals do not return to the bivouac owing to the widening of the trail. Therefore, it was inferred that the spread of the width of the trail could be suppressed by changing the constant μ used for the probability π calculated when deciding the movement destination according to the state. μ is a parameter representing the attraction rate without pheromones. However, because individuals who can return to the bivouac do not have to go to a position without pheromones, individuals with $S=2$ are set to $\mu=0$, and the experiments with these settings are performed. This means that individuals that return to the bivouac with food do not search at all and follow the pheromone completely. Although real army ant individuals with this behavior have not yet been confirmed, this experiment introduced the above settings to express the transition of the multidirectional to unidirectional raid. The results are shown in Figs. 11 and 12.

Fig. 11 Movement of the individuals with $S=2$ when $\mu=0$. Blue dots represent food, red dots on the upper right, and gray dots on the other. The color of the red dots becomes dense as the number of individuals is increased in the position with the individuals. There are no individuals who cannot return to the bivouac. By setting $\mu=0$ for the individual with $S=2$, the width of the trail can be suppressed. Additionally, because the individuals with $S=2$ have no ability to search, it is easier for them to be attracted to strong pheromones.

As can be observed in Fig. 11, there are no individuals who cannot return to the bivouac. By setting $\mu=0$ for the individual with $S=2$, the width of the trail can be suppressed. Additionally, because the individuals with $S=2$ come to have no ability to search, it is easier for them to be attracted to strong pheromones. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 12, the

concentration of pheromones laid on the trail used many times increases.

From the results so far, by setting $\mu=0$ for the individuals with $S=2$, it was possible to obtain a tree-like pattern without producing individuals who cannot enter the bivouac. Therefore, we next examine whether it is possible to switch trails by periodically switching the feeding area.

Fig. 12 The pheromone trail made by the individuals with $S=2$ when $\mu=0$ on the entire map. The square with many pheromones is plotted in red and dark. The concentration of the pheromones laid on a trail used many times become high.

From the results of Figs. 13 and 14, it is deduced that the direction of the tree-like pattern is also switched by switching the feeding area. Further, immediately after the feeding area is switched (near 3000 steps in Fig. 13(a) to 13(b), 6000 steps in Fig. 13(b) to 13(c), and 9000 steps in Fig. 13(c) to 13(d)), it can be observed that the number of individuals heading in the direction in which the food has been decreases rapidly, and the number of individuals into the bivouac increases. Moreover, we confirmed that finding new food by the individuals induced the movement of many other individuals toward the new food.

IV. DISCUSSION

From the results shown in Fig. 6, it can be observed that other surrounding individuals are attracted to the pheromones released by individuals who cannot enter the bivouac, and strange behavior occurs. In other words, when extending the Solé model in multiple directions, it is necessary to consider whether it is possible for the individuals to return to the bivouac completely. In this study, we tried two methods: one is an automatic return to the bivouac

Fig. 13 Difference between areas concentrating the individuals when changing the area to put the food for every fixed period. Blue and red dots represent the food and individuals, respectively. The food area is exchanged from (a) to (b), (b) to (c), and (c) to (d) every 3,000 steps. The color of the red dots becomes denser as the number of individuals is increased in the position with the individuals.

Fig. 14 Dynamics of the number of individuals heading to a position with food when the position changes periodically. The x-axis indicates the number of steps, and the y-axis indicates the number of individuals.

when the individuals returning to the bivouac came to close to the bivouac position, and the other is not letting the individuals return to the bivouac at all. First, we tried a method of automatic returning individuals to the bivouac when they came too close to the bivouac. As shown in Figs. 8 to 10, when the individuals who went to the upper right return to the bivouac, the width of the pheromone trail spreads, and some individuals who cannot enter the bivouac come out. As a cause of expanding the width of the pheromone trail, it can be considered that the returning individuals progress to a position with a low pheromone concentration. That is,

because the returning individuals release large amounts of pheromones, if they go to a position with a low pheromone concentration even once, the pheromone concentration at that position may increase and subsequent individuals may move further outward from that position. From these, it turns out that it is not enough to automatically return to the bivouac when the individuals come near it.

Therefore, we confirmed a simulation experiment with a setting that individuals never explore while returning to the bivouac. As shown in Figs. 11 and 12, the trail converges to the bivouac without spreading. From the above two attempts, it can be inferred that simply modifying the Solé model so that it can be directed in the eight directions is not sufficient to express the pattern transition. From the results of Figs. 13 and 14, it is inferred that changing the position of the food increases the number of individuals moving in the food direction, and a tree-like pattern is created in the food direction. This result was obtained by making a modification that the individuals in the Solé model can select one direction from eight directions when leaving the bivouac and making changes to enable returning to the bivouac with absolute accuracy as described above. The Solé model is a model in which one of the three positions in front of the individual are selected, and that movement is iterated until the individual finds food; when the food is found, it is rotated 180 degrees, and the same type of movement is repeated to return to the bivouac. Therefore, the individual moves only in the forward direction in the eight-ways model because our model is based on the Solé model.

From these facts, to express the pattern transition, it is necessary for the individual to move only in the forward direction, and also for the returning individual to move in accordance with only the pheromone so that all individuals can completely return to the bivouac.

The eight-ways model proposed in this study also has drawbacks. When individuals completely follow the pheromones when returning to the bivouac, it means that if individuals are in an area without pheromones, they will be immobile. Moreover, depending on the decay rate of the pheromones and the renewal frequency, it is considered that the pheromone trail may be broken, so that the individual cannot return to the bivouac. This is a problem because when the pattern transition from radial to tree-like is viewed as a search system, it will not hold as one if an individual cannot return to the bivouac. Therefore, to establish this pattern transition as a system, it is considered necessary to clarify the influence of the decay rate of the pheromone and the renewal frequency on the continuation of the

pheromone trail. Further, it is necessary to clarify a method in which returning individuals can be returned to the bivouac with absolute accuracy, even when they go to an area without pheromones.

The actual length of the pheromone trail of army ants varies depending on the species, such as approximately 150 m for *Eciton Burchelli* [3] and approximately 30 m for *Dorylus Wilverthi* [5]. Assuming that homing individuals in the real army ants completely decide their destination according to the pheromones, there may be a relation between the pheromone trail length and the pheromone volatilization rate, or the number of individuals going to the tip of the trail.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we focused on the emergent transition of characteristic patterns observed in army ants during swarm raids. The studies focusing only on the tree-like patterns include those of Deneubourg et al. and Solé et al. However, the models proposed in these two studies could not express the multidirectional to unidirectional convergence that is observed in the real world. Therefore, we proposed an eight-ways model that is an improvement of the Solé model and verified whether the transition can be emerged using our model. From the results, we found the necessary factors to consider when obtaining the state transition of raiding patterns as follows:

- A simple modification of the Solé model directed in only eight directions is not sufficient to emerge the pattern transition from radial to tree-like.
- To emerge the pattern transition, it is necessary for the returning individuals to surely return to the bivouac.
- To ensure that the returning individuals can return to the bivouac, they should not explore positions without pheromones and should follow the pheromone trail completely when returning.
- Moving individuals forward when leaving from and returning to the bivouac play an important role in emerging the pattern transition from radial to tree-like.

Assuming that the pattern transitions are obtained through evolution, it is considered to be a form adapted to some environment.

In future work, therefore, if the features of the environment in which the ants show the pattern transitions are clarified, there is a possibility that the pattern transition can be applied in engineering.

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